

A Study of Compound Action Potentials in Current-Coupled Tracts: the General Case

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Abstract

In this paper, the authors investigate compound action potentials formed when the underlying tract's axons have current-mediated coupling amongst themselves, and no field-mediated coupling. The key finding of the paper is that, for the case of biophysically inhomogeneous axon tracts, the compound action potential is governed by a Hodgkin-Huxley like equation itself in certain cases. The paper extends an earlier result for the identical axon case.

1 Introduction

The compound action potential is a more relevant quantity than the single-fiber action potential for the neurophysiologist who does not often have access to individual fiber voltages, though its relevance is less for single neuron investigations. Thus its detailed study is of some importance. In this paper, we take an analytical approach and develop the resulting compounded signal equation. Some of the questions we are interested in answering include: Can a nerve be treated like an axon (Hodgkin & Huxley, 1952) mathematically when compounded? If so, can there be inter-nerve current- or field-mediated coupling (Chawla, 2017), say, when there is minimal insulation (Reutskiy *et al.*, 2003) on the considered nerves? Further, if a nerve is like an axon, then all synapses emerging from a given nerve may not only be synchronized, but they may act as one unified, though distributed synapse. So, can nerve formation be seen as a case of the organism trying to accomplish a task requiring amplification of the control signal? In this paper, we don't directly address all these questions, but our work illuminates some of them.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we review an important paper from the literature. Then we present a table of notation. In Section 3 we describe the model being studied for two identical axons and in Section 4 we extend it to the general case. Finally, we conclude in Section 5.

2 Wijesinghe’s Model: a Review

Prior theoretical work on compound action potentials includes (Wijesinghe *et al.*, 1991), (Stegeman & De Weerd, 1982), (Briaire & Frijns, 2005) as well as (Kim & Kim, 1976), and experimental papers include (Dallos & Cheatham, 1976), (Stys *et al.*, 1991), (Lai *et al.*, 2002), (Bolton *et al.*, 1981), (Stypulkowski & Van den Honert, 1984), (Bourien *et al.*, 2014), (Abbas *et al.*, 1999), (Bolton & Carter, 1980), while clinical work includes (He *et al.*, 2017). In this literature review we will focus on (Wijesinghe *et al.*, 1991) wherein the authors study the compound action potential and develop a model for its description on the basis of single fiber action potentials. They study the effect of the myelin sheath and also the effects of temperature and fiber diameter on the compound action potential. Their forward model consists of summations of the single fiber action signals where each signal is time-shifted by the corresponding delay τ_j between the stimulus time and the arrival time at the recording electrode of that fiber. They present a block diagram for the compound action current (CAC) and present an algorithm for computing the compound action signal. They present time-domain simulation results. They also study variation of the peak-to-peak amplitude of anisotropy of the nerve bundle. Their principal result is the relation between the conduction velocity distribution and the specific compound action potential studied.

Notation

The notation used in this paper is succinctly summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Table of Notation

S. No.	Symbol	Meaning
1	C, C_1, C_2	fiber capacitance per unit length
2	$\alpha_{\{1,2\}}, \beta_{\{1,2\}}$	constants related to intra- and extra-cellular resistivity, summarizing the constants in (Reutskiy <i>et al.</i> , 2003)
3	$g_{\{1,2\}}$	constant related to conductance of myelin
4	$V_{\{1,2\}}$	transmembrane potential
5	$\tau_{\{1,2\}}$	time delay between stimulus onset and the action potential initiation time

3 Identical Axons: The Model and Its Study

In this section, we recall the work done in (Chawla, 2023). As per (Wijesinghe *et al.*, 1991), under the assumption of superposition, the compounded action potential (CAP) is given in terms of time-shifted versions of the single fiber action potentials:

$$CAP(x, t) = \sum_{j=1}^N V_j(v_j, t - \tau_j) \quad (1)$$

where τ_j is the time-delay between the stimulus onset and the arrival time at the j -th fiber, x is the propagation distance, and the variables v_j represent the conduction velocities of the various fibers. In (Wijesinghe *et al.*, 1991), the v_j are distinct; in our case, they are identical. Nevertheless a variable propagation delay arises due to the geometry of the situation (Chawla *et al.*, 2019). More specifically, as in (Chawla *et al.*, 2021), these delays are related to the action potential initiation times at the current-coupled axons.

Consider the (Reutskiy *et al.*, 2003) equations for two coupled axons (that is, $N = 2$), both being identical biophysically¹:

$$C \frac{\partial V_1}{\partial t} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 V_1(t)}{\partial x^2} + \beta \frac{\partial^2 V_2(t)}{\partial x^2} - gV_1 \quad (2)$$

and

$$C \frac{\partial V_2}{\partial t} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 V_2(t)}{\partial x^2} + \beta \frac{\partial^2 V_1(t)}{\partial x^2} - gV_2 \quad (3)$$

Next, let $V = V_1(t - \tau_1) + V_2(t - \tau_2)$ be the compounded signal. Then,

$$C \frac{\partial V(t)}{\partial t} = (\alpha + \beta) \frac{\partial^2 V(t)}{\partial x^2} - gV(t) \quad (4)$$

is the equation for the compounded signal. This resembles the Hodgkin-Huxley equation for a single fiber (Hodgkin & Huxley, 1952). Thus, the compounded signal's propagation is similar to that of the single fiber signal, in the case considered (identical current-coupled fibers).

4 General Axons: The Model and its Study

In this section, we relax the values α and β , allowing them to be different for the component axons. For the following two axons,

$$C_1 \frac{\partial V_1}{\partial t} = \alpha_1 \frac{\partial^2 V_1(t)}{\partial x^2} + \beta_1 \frac{\partial^2 V_2(t)}{\partial x^2} - g_1 V_1 \quad (5)$$

and

$$C_2 \frac{\partial V_2}{\partial t} = \alpha_2 \frac{\partial^2 V_2(t)}{\partial x^2} + \beta_2 \frac{\partial^2 V_1(t)}{\partial x^2} - g_2 V_2 \quad (6)$$

we obtain the following linear matrix equation,

$$C' \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \begin{bmatrix} V_1 \\ V_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 & \beta_1 \\ \alpha_2 & \beta_2 \end{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \begin{bmatrix} V_1 \\ V_2 \end{bmatrix} - G \begin{bmatrix} V_1 \\ V_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

¹The velocity variables are omitted, being identical.

where

$$C' = \begin{bmatrix} C_1 & 0 \\ 0 & C_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

and

$$G = \begin{bmatrix} g_1 & 0 \\ 0 & g_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

If we express it compactly, using

$$V' = \begin{bmatrix} V_1 \\ V_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

and

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 & \beta_1 \\ \alpha_2 & \beta_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

we see that we have an equation in the form of the equation of a single axon:

$$C' \frac{\partial}{\partial t} V' = A \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} V' - G V' \quad (12)$$

Take two such ‘single’ axons (for a total of four axons), each with the same properties (C', A, G) , and using the result from Section 3, we find that if we couple them as per Equations (2) and (3), and compound them as per Equation (4), this compounded signal again follows the single axon law. This is explicated as follows.

The ‘single axons’ are,

$$C' \frac{\partial}{\partial t} V'_1 = A \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} V'_1 - G V'_1 \quad (13)$$

and

$$C' \frac{\partial}{\partial t} V'_2 = A \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} V'_2 - G V'_2. \quad (14)$$

where

$$V'_1 = \begin{bmatrix} V_1 \\ V_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

and

$$V'_2 = \begin{bmatrix} V_3 \\ V_4 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (16)$$

Upon cross-coupling them, we have

$$C' \frac{\partial}{\partial t} V'_1 = A \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} V'_1 + B \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} V'_2 - G V'_1 \quad (17)$$

and

$$C' \frac{\partial}{\partial t} V_2' = A \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} V_2' + B \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} V_1' - G V_2'. \quad (18)$$

Next we define,

$$V_3' = V_1' + V_2' \quad (19)$$

to be the (partially) compounded signal. This will obey the law,

$$C' \frac{\partial V_3'}{\partial t} = (A + B) \frac{\partial^2 V_3'}{\partial x^2} - G V_3'. \quad (20)$$

In this way, we find that certain combinations of (not necessarily all identical) coupled axons yield very simple compound action potentials that follow the usual Hodgkin-Huxley (vector) law. By mathematical induction, Equation (20) can likely be extended into a more general statement, for arbitrary numbers of axons. Following the guidelines of the previous and present sections, the compounded signals might generally contain 2^n voltage components where $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

5 Discussion and Conclusion

To summarize, in this paper we found that when the underlying current-coupled axons are biophysically identical in pairs, then the compounded signal may be like a Hodgkin-Huxley signal. A limitation of our work is that we didn't explore the case of sensorimotor nerves wherein individual fibers carry signals in two opposing directions. In future work, we can also consider simulations of the propagation of ephaptic CAPs (eCAPs) under focal demyelination conditions (Waxman & Brill, 1978). Another investigation that may yield novel insight is the impact of single fiber internodal lengths on the conduction velocity of eCAPs. However, the most important aspect of the present work, even beyond (Chawla, 2023), is that it illumines future studies of quantum effects for entire nerves, in the context of (Chawla, 2022) and (Chawla & Morgera, 2022).

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